

Removing barriers to advanced imaging and machine learning-based analysis

Jodie R Malcolm^{1,2}, Stuart Lacy³, Andrea Papaleo⁴, Le Liu⁴, Suleiman H Kwairanga^{5,6}, Graeme Park⁷, Joanne Marrison⁷, Richard Kasprowicz⁸, Kerry Hallbrook⁹, Richard Williams¹⁰, Kildare Miranda¹¹, Teng-Leong Chew¹², Caron A Jacobs¹³, Mahmoud Maina^{5,6}, Ana Paula C A Lima¹¹, Jeremy C Mottram^{1,2}, Beth Cimini⁴, Ben Powell¹⁴, Peter O'Toole⁷, Laura Wiggins¹⁵, William J Brackenbury^{1,2*}

¹ Jack Birch Cancer Research Unit, Department of Biology, University of York, Heslington, York, UK

² York Biomedical Research Institute, Department of Biology, University of York, Heslington, York, UK

³ IT Services, University of York, Heslington, York, UK

⁴ Imaging Platform, Broad Institute of MIT and Harvard, Cambridge, MA, USA

⁵ Biomedical Science Research and Training Centre, Yobe State University, Damaturu, Nigeria

⁶ Sussex Neuroscience, School of Life Sciences, University of Sussex, Brighton, UK

⁷ Bioscience Technology Facility, Department of Biology, University of York, Heslington, York, YO10 5DD, UK

⁸ GlaxoSmithKline Medicines Research Centre, Stevenage, UK

⁹ UK Cell Culture and Banking, Discovery Sciences, AstraZeneca, Cambridge, UK

¹⁰ ioLight, Whitchurch, Hampshire, UK

¹¹ Instituto de Biofisica Carlos Chagas Filho, Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil

¹² Advanced Imaging Center and Integrative Imaging, Howard Hughes Medical Institute Janelia Research Campus, Ashburn, VA, USA

¹³ Department of Pathology and Institute of Infectious Disease and Molecular Medicine, University of Cape Town, Cape Town, South Africa

¹⁴ Department of Mathematics, University of York, Heslington, York, UK

¹⁵ School of Chemical, Materials and Biological Engineering, University of Sheffield,
Sheffield, UK

* Corresponding author.

Abstract

Global and community-driven initiatives have recently achieved considerable success in overcoming key challenges that hinder the widespread adoption of advanced microscopy and bioimage analysis tools in under-resourced settings. To build upon this progress, we held a workshop in May 2025 at the University of York, UK to address the needs and barriers associated with implementing time-lapse imaging and machine learning-based phenotyping in low-resource research environments. We focussed on identifying the specific challenges faced by existing networks represented at the meeting, emphasising how integrating combined imaging hardware and machine learning-based approaches can solve these problems. This article summarises the key observations and actionable strategies from the workshop. The proposed steps aim to significantly increase the dissemination and uptake of these powerful technologies to advance biological research in low-resource settings globally.

Introduction

Significant progress has been made in advancing imaging technologies to enable extraction of high quality information from light microscopy images, thus enabling characterisation of processes including cellular proliferation (Antonelli *et al.*, 2023), differentiation (Lin *et al.*, 2017), migration (Smith *et al.*, 2016), and response to treatments (Chandrasekaran *et al.*, 2024). Moreover, by adding repeated measurements of live cell cultures to generate time-lapse imaging data, it is also possible to gain insight into dynamic changes in cellular behaviour over time (Paniagua-Herranz *et al.*, 2020; Wiggins *et al.*, 2023). However, such measurements typically rely on data obtained using high cost systems, including advanced confocal, super-resolution or ptychographic microscopy. In addition, emerging machine learning-based image analysis tools and approaches often require significant computational resources, which depend on stable, fast access to the cloud, and/or costly hardware.

The Technopolis Group's recent barrier survey identified high costs of imaging equipment and limited access to analysis software as major hurdles impeding progress of bio-imaging research in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) (Davé *et al.*, 2023). The survey also highlighted that, despite resource constraints, data interoperability is essential to enable researchers in LMICs to extract and analyse relevant information (Davé *et al.*, 2023). The proliferation of an array of low-cost and open source light microscopes presents an opportunity to increase uptake of such imaging techniques and image analysis technologies to researchers in LMICs. However, these low-cost systems also present challenges, particularly in relation to data quality and imaging modality. In particular, low-cost imaging systems are often limited to brightfield acquisition, and are more susceptible to artefacts including noise, vignetting, blur, distortion, and sensor defects, and very few are designed for mammalian live-cell imaging. Further interconnected challenges include creating awareness of such technologies, improving access, incentivising continued use, addressing appropriate

local scientific needs, and encouraging sharing and investment, discussed extensively elsewhere (Aaron *et al.*, 2025).

To increase dissemination and uptake of advanced light microscopy and image analysis technologies, it is necessary to develop tools and workflows that can extract relevant information without the need for high cost imaging equipment or high performance computing hardware. The first step in such workflows is acquisition, where an appropriate balance needs to be struck between frugality of the microscope and minimum requirements for imaging quality to enable production of meaningful research-level datasets (Walzik *et al.*, 2015; Aaron *et al.*, 2025). In addition, emerging approaches such as U-Nets, generative adversarial networks (GANs), and diffusion models, which can enable label-free organelle prediction using data acquired on high-end systems (Christiansen *et al.*, 2018; Ounkomol *et al.*, 2018; Guo *et al.*, 2020; Cross-Zamirski *et al.*, 2022, 2023), need to be adapted so that they can be used with data from low-cost systems.

In May 2025, we held a workshop at the University of York, UK, to discuss needs and barriers to time-lapse imaging and machine learning-based phenotyping in low-resource settings. The meeting focused on identifying the challenges faced via existing networks, including the African Bioimaging Consortium (ABIC), the Biomedical Science Research and Training Centre (BioRTC) (Maina, 2023), the Africa Microscopy Initiative (AMI) (Reiche *et al.*, 2023), and Latin America Bioimaging (LABI), and how combined imaging hardware and machine learning-based approaches can address these challenges (Aaron & Chew, 2025). This article summarises key observations from the workshop and steps identified to increase dissemination and uptake of these technologies.

Barriers to advanced imaging and image analysis in low resource settings

A range of interconnected barriers significantly contribute to the inequitable dissemination and adoption of advanced imaging and analysis among researchers in LMICs. To address this inequity, our recent discussions with integral stake-holders from under-resourced regions identified key challenges that disproportionately affect researchers from such backgrounds. We hope these insights will inform more inclusive strategies for the propagation of advanced microscopy technologies and machine learning-based bioimage analysis tools.

Education and training

To effectively distribute and preserve knowledge in advanced microscopy, education and training opportunities are paramount; not only for mastering standard laboratory techniques, but also for developing and maintaining expertise in image acquisition and downstream analysis (Haase *et al.*, 2024; Cimini *et al.*, 2024). However, significant barriers impede LMIC capacity building, which necessitates prompt action to enable rapid propulsion in locally-directed research output (De Niz *et al.*, 2024).

Mentorship is vital for meaningful scientific progress. By encouraging junior researchers to take ownership of their ideas, learning, and development, guided by an experienced mentor, knowledge transfer becomes intuitive and instinctive. This dynamic not only advances education and training, but also promotes a culture of investing into the success of future researchers (Lescano *et al.*, 2019). As highlighted during our meeting, structured mentoring schemes are uncommon in low resource settings, and often considered inadequate when measured against high-income country (HIC) standards (Kpokiri *et al.*, 2024). Most mentoring guidelines are developed with the assumption of abundant resources, which makes uptake in low-resource settings particularly challenging, largely owing to insufficient

consideration for these disparities (Chi *et al.*, 2019). As such, tailored “mentoring-the-mentor” or “training-the-trainer” initiatives specifically developed within the context and culture of LMICs have been designed to spearhead investment and implementation of mentoring practices within institutional settings (Lescano *et al.*, 2019).

In addition to low adoption of mentoring programmes, there is a general lack of access to education and training opportunities for researchers in LMICs, which further contributes to poor knowledge dissemination (Launois *et al.*, 2021). The same channels of information available to researchers in HICs and which deliver critical insight surrounding prospective conferences, workshops or teaching events, often do not have the same reach in local communities encompassed by poor infrastructure constraints (see *Insufficient Physical and Technical Infrastructure*). As such, training opportunities that would be pivotal to career development and could establish crucial international connections, provide unique expert education on relevant imaging technologies or foster essential bioimage analysis knowledge exchange, are disproportionately over-represented by HIC versus LMIC attendees (Velin *et al.*, 2021).

Geographical limitations also prohibit entry to important research facilities for specialist training programs. While bioimaging training hubs including the BioRTC exist to overcome training inadequacies (Isah *et al.*, 2024), travel bursaries may be needed for bioimaging scientists to access such facilities and carry out research or receive expert training. However, global inequality in funding opportunities and grant success in favour of HIC populations further disadvantages researchers in resource constrained settings seeking opportunity for technical advancement and professional development (Charani *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, training in grant writing and research management is also not widely available across LMIC institutions, impacting the quality and competitiveness of applications (Chikwari *et al.*, 2024). Building capacity in grantsmanship is therefore essential for enabling LMIC researchers to secure funding.

The AMI is pioneering change in access to microcopy training and networking opportunities (Reiche *et al.*, 2023). By delivering all-expenses-paid high-level microscopy and analysis courses, with plans to run themed workshops to tackle pertinent health challenges in local communities, the AMI is an exemplary approach to promote the use of microscopy in countries where such technologies are not widely used.

In summary, our recent meeting underscored how barriers to education and training for bioimage scientists significantly impair adoption and implementation of reliable bioimage analysis workflows. Sufficient mentoring and training opportunities are essential for researchers in low-resource settings to become proficient in bioimage analysis, foster international collaborations delivering impact, and make significant advancements in locally-relevant health research. Inequalities in funding opportunities and success rates compound these challenges by exacerbating the lack of formal training pathways and perpetuating systemic barriers in resource-constrained locations.

Lack of technical specialists

A significant consequence of the limited education and training opportunities in bioimage analysis described above is a shortage of technical specialists in core facilities or research institutes. Technical specialists are crucial for sustaining and developing bioimage analysis capabilities, with key roles including: (i) managing day-to-day operations of the research facility, (ii) maintaining the microscopes(s), and (iii) providing training on microscope usage, data collection, analysis, and interpretation (Brown, 2018). Given the high turnover of research staff and students in many institutions, technical specialists are therefore essential for retaining institutional knowledge of bioimage practices (Hubble *et al.*, 2020). In particular, trained bioimage analysts preserve expertise in advanced microscopy, manage large-scale storage, and regularly use complex image analysis tools, but fewer than 25% of these

critically-needed specialists work outside of Europe or North America (Corbat *et al.*, 2025). Low retention rates of technical specialists in LMICs further exacerbates this issue. The so-called “brain-drain” of trained researchers migrating from LMICs to HICs highlights the challenges scientists face in resource-constrained settings when it comes to building research capacity and accessing bioimaging for their research (Ahmed *et al.*, 2020). Lack of relevant technical expertise in LMICs can perpetuate poor uptake and use of advanced microscopy and analysis in core facilities and research institutes, and may impede important discoveries essential to progressing region-specific research.

Compounding these issues is the often limited technical support offered by international suppliers of microscopy platforms and image analysis tools. While researchers in HICs frequently benefit from around-the-clock assistance if an instrument breaks down or requires specialist support, those in LMICs may experience significant delays and cost before a service engineer can attend their site. These delays can be further impeded by poor internet connection and time zone differences, which hinder the effectiveness of remote troubleshooting and support. In addition, the pace at which parts can be imported to replace broken components provides a further bottleneck. Even if cutting-edge microscopes are donated or purchased by researchers in LMICs, the lack of access to local service engineers and spare parts means these instruments risk being underutilised and creates a dependency on external collaborators for access to advanced imaging opportunities (Davé *et al.*, 2023).

Taken together, inadequate access to bioimage-centred education and training in LMICs prohibits access to and retention of essential technical experts, who are fundamental in sustaining institutional knowledge of microscopy technologies and analytical tools. Restricted access to manufacturers’ technical support presents a further issue for researchers in low resource settings. Such challenges risk making advanced microscopy and bioimage analysis less attractive approaches for scientists looking to address key research questions in their local communities.

Insufficient physical and technical infrastructure

For the adoption of advanced microscopy and bioimage analysis in LMICs, there are considerable physical and technical infrastructure challenges. Here, we define physical infrastructure to include tangible, material resources such as an operable research laboratory and essential microscopy equipment hardware, whereas technical infrastructure encompasses the digital tools and computing resources that are essential for storing and processing large bioimage datasets.

There is inequitable access to affordable and reliable electricity, with the majority of those most disadvantaged populating sub-Saharan Africa (Farquharson *et al.*, 2018). These challenges arise as a result of systemic issues, including a lack of electricity-use frameworks (Brew-Hammond & Kemausuor, 2009; Brew-Hammond, 2010), unreliable electrical supply (Adair-Rohani *et al.*, 2013), a lack of financial investment (Gujba *et al.*, 2012; Szabó *et al.*, 2016) and infrastructure inadequacies (Gregory & Sovacool, 2019). Invariably, these issues result in disproportionate access to electrical supply and frequent power outages across the African continent (Farquharson *et al.*, 2018). To a lesser extent, electricity generation and distribution is also an ongoing challenge for other LMICs, including across Latin America and Caribbean (LAC) countries. For many LACs, more than 70% of electricity is generated using renewable sources, with hydropower contributing substantially to this distribution. However, despite significant economic growth over the last decade and substantial uptake of renewable energy to accommodate electrical requirements, many LACs still lack reliable and renewable electricity supply (González-Lorente *et al.*, 2024).

While poor electrical distribution has significant consequences for growth and economic potential of LMICs, it adds additional constraints to research facilities which require reliable electricity supply to support running advanced microscopes, and for culturing live cells, as

well as cold storage temperatures for research samples and consumables. A reliable supply of electricity is of particular importance for time-series experiments using live cells and/or tissues. In addition, data storage and use of High Performance Computing (HPC) systems for data processing is one of the most energy-intensive scientific endeavours (Suarez *et al.*, 2025), and again relies on provision of a reliable electricity supply. To overcome these limitations, diesel generators are often used to accommodate electrical requirements in low resource settings (Marais & Wiedinmyer, 2016). However, the use of generators has environmental and economic implications (Jacal *et al.*, 2022). The actual costs vary widely depending on the local price of fuel, however it is estimated to range from three- to seven-times the cost of purchasing electricity directly from the grid (Foster & Steinbuks, 2009; Farquharson *et al.*, 2018; Jacal *et al.*, 2022).

The cost of advanced microscopy systems, such as confocal, super-resolution, and quantitative phase imaging (QPI) microscopes, can exceed hundreds of thousands of dollars to purchase. For many LMIC institutions, these costs are prohibitive, creating a barrier to bioimaging research. Initiatives such as the AMI aim to address this gap by establishing shared imaging hubs to provide equitable access to high-end instruments and training (Reiche *et al.*, 2023). Complementary strategies exist such as the OpenFlexure, OpenFrame and Squid, which offer customisable microscopes that can be locally manufactured using 3D-printing and open-source designs, at a fraction of commercial costs (Li *et al.*, 2020; Lightley *et al.*, 2023; Knapper *et al.*, 2024). Critically, these affordable systems have the capacity to address pressing research questions in health and disease (Collins *et al.*, 2020; Rosen *et al.*, 2024; Knapper *et al.*, 2024). However, frugal microscopes can be perceived as being “not research grade”, limiting their integration into research workflows. Validation studies and community-driven standards are needed to shift this perception and promote adoption in resource-limited settings (Aaron *et al.*, 2025).

An additional consideration given that modern bioimage analysis workflows are often computationally exhaustive, is limited network bandwidth and intermittent internet connectivity, and reliance on low-cost computers or mobile phones to access the web (Biga *et al.*, 2024; Ghedira *et al.*, 2024; Nacis *et al.*, 2024). This severely restricts the use of advanced bioimaging analysis pipelines, constraining research progress. Furthermore, in our experience, high-resolution QPI modalities such as the PhaseFocus LiveCyte or the Tomocube HT-X1 can easily generate large-scale datasets ranging from hundreds of gigabytes to several terabytes in size. Storing and processing these data requires GPUs, HPC clusters, and/or reliable cloud access, which are often not readily accessible in LMIC research environments. While cloud-based data processing solutions exist, their adoption is constrained by connectivity issues and cost barriers for sustained use (Davé *et al.*, 2023). The lack of affordable computing infrastructure further compounds the challenge of storing and processing large datasets generated by high-end microscopes.

Other Considerations

Additional barriers to advanced microscopy and image analysis workflows were discussed extensively during our exchange with researchers in underserved scientific communities. High-quality sample preparation is fundamental for advanced imaging, yet researchers in LMICs frequently face barriers in accessing essential reagents and consumables, such as antibodies, Foetal Bovine Serum (FBS) and trypsin, owing to restrictive import policies, high costs and long delivery times. These constraints can significantly delay experiments and limit reproducibility, underscoring the need for regional reagent hubs and open-source protocols to mitigate supply chain vulnerabilities.

Critically, the increasing cost of accessing and publishing in research journals deprives skilled researchers in resource-constrained settings. While there has been a positive trend in institutional open access (OA) publishing since 2008 (Shu & Larivière, 2024), disparities

remain for researchers in LMICs who encounter disproportionately higher costs for publishing primary research in OA journals, or face limited global reach under current publishing policies (Kilgallon *et al.*, 2023).

Collaborative research is a cornerstone of modern science, but institutional policies can sometimes create disincentives. In some LMIC research environments, promotion and performance evaluation systems prioritise first or corresponding authorship, reducing the perceived value of multi-author publications. This can discourage participation in large, collaborative projects that are essential for capacity building and global integration. Reforming academic reward systems to recognise diverse contributions, such as data sharing, method development, and training, would help foster more equitable collaborations.

In summary, there are multiple local and systemic challenges faced by researchers in low-resource settings when implementing advanced microscopy and bioimage analysis workflows to tackle urgent regional health challenges. These issues stretch beyond funding disparities and include limited training opportunities in bioimage analysis, inadequate physical and technical infrastructure, and institutional governance that may not encourage collaboration and knowledge sharing. Critically, these are not stand-alone issues with straightforward solutions. They are deeply interconnected, forming a vicious cycle (Figure 1). Researchers in resource-constrained settings often lack the preliminary data needed to submit competitive grant applications, yet without funding, they cannot generate the data required to secure that funding. This catch-22 perpetuates inequality and hinders progress in building sustainable research capacity in bioimage analysis.

Figure 1. Barriers to advanced imaging and analysis are interconnected and compound one another. Key challenges including limited education and training, inadequate infrastructure, and a shortage of technical expertise impede the generation of preliminary data, which is crucial for securing competitive research grants. These issues do not exist in isolation; instead, they form a cyclical pattern of obstacles that collectively hinder the production of high-quality research focused on locally relevant health concerns. The absence of preliminary data perpetuates economic constraints, which in turn restrict the development of training programs, infrastructure, and local technical capacity, thus continuing the cycle.

Progress and future directions

During our meeting, we reflected on how achieving widespread access to advanced imaging and analysis in low-resource settings relies on progress in three interconnected areas: strong networks and capacity-building programmes that support training, collaboration and sustainability; the development of low-cost, accessible hardware; and development of image analysis software with machine learning capabilities that can run on modest computing infrastructure. Progress in each of these areas is already underway, and here we highlight examples that reflect advances in practice, ranging from innovative hardware and software solutions through to community-driven initiatives.

Geographical and organisational structures enable success

Successful collaboration, particularly in the global south, depends on overcoming administrative and infrastructure barriers, such as customs restrictions, visa limitations, and low data bandwidth, and access to appropriate low-cost, low maintenance instrumentation. This is particularly the case for travelling researchers and expert technologists, as well as movement of samples, and, to a lesser extent, data. Adopting a hub-and-node model, with a central well-supported coordinating hub, may facilitate formation of networks connecting regional centres of excellence across the global south with wider nodes using the more affordable imaging platforms (De Niz *et al.*, 2024).

There are numerous examples of existing collaborative programmes supporting bioimaging research in LMICs (Table 1). When considering development of new networks and/or extension of existing programmes, it is essential to complement these partnerships and avoid redundancy by pursuing opportunities to enhance existing initiatives and promote interoperability with ongoing projects. It is also necessary to set appropriate participation

criteria and accountability frameworks that ensure resources are used transparently and effectively.

Opportunities to engage with industry should also be sought during development, particularly given the recent acceleration in development, deployment and deprecation of microscopy technologies. For example, large pharmaceutical companies offer critical bioimaging research assets but may be hesitant to share them. Bioimaging networks need to develop mutually beneficial arrangements with such organisations and ethical frameworks that enable responsible equipment and data (re)use.

Finally, it is essential to balance short-term research goals with potential for long-term impact such that initial phases prioritise generating pilot data to support future investment, while longer-term strategies focus on ensuring sustainability of new technologies and their uptake beyond the initial funding cycle. A critical element of this prioritisation is to embed frequent horizon scanning to enable planning for research agility through enabling flexible, modular workflows that support innovation and local responsiveness to changing research priorities.

Table 1. Community-driven initiatives to support bioimaging research in LMICs

Initiative	Description	Benefit to LMICs
African Bioimaging Consortium (ABIC)	A network of imaging scientists and life science researchers with an interest in and use for microscopy throughout Africa. It aims to unite the African microscopy community and support the development of bioimaging across the continent. It is supported by the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (CZI) "Expanding Global Access to Bioimaging" program.	The Consortium provides a mechanism for sharing and accessing information, ideas and expertise. Additionally, members collaborate to build community-based solutions to key challenges and coordinate in order to engage with vendors, policy makers and global partners.
Africa Microscopy Initiative (AMI)	A multi-faceted program focused on increasing access to and expertise in bioimaging throughout Africa. It achieves this through the open access AMI Imaging Centre, which offers African scientists access to advanced microscopy equipment and support on an application basis, along with various training and teaching programs including workshops and webinars. AMI also facilitates the equipment distribution Program for Equipment Exchange & Reutilization (PEER), which partners with commercial organisations to distribute pre-owned, high-quality microscopes to institutions across the continent.	Equipment and expertise are shared in tandem across a community of researchers with similar priorities.
Biomedical Science Research and Training Centre (BioRTC)	A regional bioimaging hub based in Yobe State University, Nigeria. Its goal is to offer state-of-the-art core facilities and training to biomedical science researchers within and outside Nigeria, as well as fostering research collaborations.	The facility contains one of the largest concentrations of high end microscopy equipment in west Africa. The centre actively promotes open access to bioimaging technologies, provides structured training for early-career researchers, and creates opportunities for hands-on capacity building.
Global Bioimaging	A community network for all stakeholders and participants in bioimaging, funded by Horizon 2020. Particular expertise in training and knowledge transfer, delivered via webinars and job-shadowing/placements. Their Imaging for All (i4A) programme funds researchers in LMICs to visit well-resourced bioimaging facilities. To make this programme operate successfully they have developed an application process for vetting, coordinating and financing visits. Global Bioimaging also delivers "train-the-trainer"	The network provides a route to scaling up research projects, providing access to resources at one scale which are used to generate data needed to justify resources at the next scale.

	courses designed for imaging core facility professionals on how to organise and deliver effective training programs, perpetuating knowledge sharing and bioimaging community engagement.	
Imaging Africa	Hosts pan-continental, fully-funded workshops to build microscopy expertise among African researchers. Covered costs include meals, air transport and accommodation to ensure workshops are fully accessible, enabling participants from all African nations to gain hands-on training in advanced imaging techniques and strengthen the regional imaging community.	Imaging Africa directly addresses barriers faced by researchers in LMICs such as lack of training opportunities and limited funding by providing free, high-quality microscopy education.
Latin America Bioimaging (LABI)	A network of bioimaging scientists from the Latin America and Caribbean region. The initiative focuses on training, education and providing researchers in the region with access to appropriate imaging technologies.	LABI aims to strengthen and promote access to bioimaging technologies via a collaborative network encompassing training, knowledge exchange and infrastructure access.
OpenScopes Initiative	Coordinated from Imperial (with partners in India, China and South Africa and sponsored in part by BBSRC, EPSRC, MRC, Research England, CZI and the Wellcome Trust), the initiative encourages the use of flexible, modular hardware and open source software for instrument control and image analysis.	The initiative opens a path for researchers in LMICs that has minimal reliance on the most expensive proprietary microscopy products.
South Africa Bioimaging (SABI)	A national network that connects imaging scientists across the country to share expertise, support new labs, and promote best practices in microscopy. It provides access to imaging facilities and staff contacts across provinces, facilitates training opportunities, and offers protocols for image acquisition, processing, and analysis. SABI also helps researchers source key materials like fluorescent probes and integrates the South African imaging community into the broader global bioimaging network.	SABI strengthens microscopy capacity within South Africa by promoting resource sharing, standardisation and skills development. Its open-access model, training support and integration with global networks help overcome common barriers in LMICs such as limited infrastructure, fragmented expertise and difficulty accessing reagents or technical guidance.
SWIFT Awards	Mobility grants, facilitated by ABIC, that support African researchers in gaining access to advanced microscopy infrastructure, training and international collaboration opportunities. These awards are designed to make it easier for	SWIFT Awards reduce the financial and logistical barriers for researchers in LMICs by covering the costs associated with travel and equipment access. This supports the development of a more equitable and connected

	researchers in Africa to attend workshops, use imaging facilities or engage with global microscopy networks.	bioimaging research community in low-resource settings.
WAMBIAN	A network of scientists and researchers in West Africa that promote microscopy and bioimage analysis techniques within the region, provide training and support, and promote collaboration and resource sharing among members.	WAMBIAN supports LMICs by building regional expertise in microscopy, reducing the reliance on external training and equipment. It enables institutions to share knowledge, infrastructure and resources to strengthen the overall scientific ecosystem in West Africa.

Enabling knowledge sharing and synergy

Effective training is essential for the widespread adoption and longevity of advanced microscopy and bioimage analysis in low-resource settings, and excellent progress has been made (Table 1). Future programmes should aim to integrate mentorship schemes into in-person workshops, and ensure accessibility for users who have varying levels of experience with complex bioimage analysis workflows. Beyond instrument operation, training should encompass; experimental design and optimisation, piloting and troubleshooting imaging workflows, data interpretation, as well as grant writing and research management. Ongoing successful initiatives such as AMI and ABIC, and low-cost platforms like OpenFlexure can serve as practical resources for hands-on learning and local innovation. With respect to skilled technical staff, training programmes should not only include facility maintenance, software troubleshooting, pipeline resilience, as well as introduction to coding and machine learning methods, but also how to deliver effective training to imaging facility users and the next generation of bioimage analysts.

Clear communication around realistic timelines for research outputs, expectations of deliverables, and upfront acknowledgement of resource constraints and limitations is paramount to maintain trust among researchers. Open and transparent planning with stakeholders will help to align expectations between local bioimage scientists, international collaborators and funders, and will ensure that bioimaging projects remain achievable and deliver significant impact in local communities. Networks should be built around shared scientific priorities, e.g., infectious diseases, oncology, and neurobiology, as this will foster interdisciplinary collaboration and accelerate knowledge transfer. Linking projects around mutual research interests may also enable resource pooling and the development of standardised workflows, which are critical for reproducibility and scalability. In addition, global initiatives should respect and integrate regional research agendas, ensuring that projects address locally relevant scientific and medical needs. Encouraging local teams to

define their own priorities not only enhances the relevance of research but also strengthens long-term sustainability and community ownership.

Enabling access to hardware

While the hub and spoke model can help enable access to microscopes, it does not solve all access issues. We discussed how service contracts for maintaining microscopes are generally unaffordable in anything but the short term. Sourcing replacement parts is very difficult. Import times for replacement parts can also be challenging and become a significant rate limiting step to advance research. It is impractical to keep duplicate spare parts in each localised country. Even in HICs, companies are running leaner centralised stocks to decrease waste and costs. Although not a replacement for cutting-edge high-end scopes, portable microscopes may be one enabling solution, especially for the collection of preliminary data. Prices for portable microscopes vary significantly depending on customisable features such as resolution, magnification, illumination type and digital imaging capability (Table 2). Software tools and workflows should be hardware-agnostic and adaptable to both high-end and resource-constrained environments, with expectations set accordingly. There also needs to be a focus on producing tools that have acceptable performance on lower-end devices but will benefit from higher computational resources if and when they are available.

More advanced features will likely enhance performance, but may also increase cost. Thus, a minimal setup needs to be balanced against the level of information required for meaningful biological inference from microscopy images. Determining this balance is crucial for designing affordable, purpose-fit tools for research, diagnostics or education in resource-limited settings. Care is also needed to ensure that the image quality is sufficient not to frustrate the analysis and thus the end user, which can have a negative effect of discouraging microscopy rather than encouraging growth in this area. However, access to

low cost microscopes is of utmost importance to allow researchers to optimise protocols and develop initial datasets that can then help them access better equipped hubs. This approach would be akin to structural 3D electron microscopy, where most central hubs require users to have tested their samples on a local more basic system before being given precious access time on a heavily used centralised microscope.

Table 2. Recent advances in low-cost imaging hardware

Microscope	Description	Benefit to LMICs	Cost
<p>CellScope (Skandarajah <i>et al.</i>, 2014)</p>	<p>CellScope is a mobile microscopy platform that transforms a smartphone into a diagnostic tool using optical attachments. Its use in diagnostics has already been exemplified for malaria, tuberculosis, cervical cancer and ear infections.</p>	<p>1-5 μm resolution for standard versions, advanced prototypes with higher-end optics can go below 1 μm. Clips onto a smartphone and provides 20x-100x magnification, ideal for disease detection and research in LMICs where access to lab infrastructure is limited. Digitally stores and shares diagnostic images, allowing data collection for research, monitoring, and public health decision-making, even in areas without internet connectivity, with images synced once a connection becomes available.</p>	<p>Research-grade mobile microscope typically costs £4-£49, with clinical-grade smartphone attachments typically costing around £237.</p>
<p>Foldscope (Cybulski <i>et al.</i>, 2014)</p>	<p>Foldscope is an ultra-low-cost light microscope made from a lens, magnets and paper. Its lightweight and compact design makes it ideal for fieldwork, classrooms and educational outreach.</p>	<p>2 μm resolution and magnification up to 140x, suitable to observe bacteria, cells and other key biological samples. Made primarily from a single sheet of waterproof paper folded into a microscope structure, making it incredibly lightweight and compact. Uses ambient or phone-based light sources, no need for batteries, power outlets or lab infrastructure.</p>	<p>Typically costs £1 - £10 per unit.</p>
<p>Glowscope (Schaefer <i>et al.</i>, 2023)</p>	<p>The Glowscope is a DIY fluorescence microscope that transforms a smartphone or tablet into a functional microscope using simple, off-the-shelf parts.</p>	<p>Offers around 10 μm resolution with ~5x magnification, sufficient to visualise fluorescent tissues and embryos, useful in basic biomedical research and training.</p>	<p>£24-£39 per unit.</p>
<p>ioLight (https://iolight.co.uk/)</p>	<p>The ioLight microscope is a portable, high-resolution digital microscope designed for use in the field or in the lab where space and mobility are key. The microscope offers</p>	<p>1 μm resolution and up to 400x magnification, sufficient to visualise cellular structures. Works on battery, displays images directly on a smartphone or tablet, and does not require</p>	<p>£2,200 - £6,600 per unit.</p>

	time-lapse imaging capabilities for observing dynamic processes.	internet access. Designed for mobile use in veterinary clinics, agricultural fields, environmental surveys, and incubators.	
Matchboxscope (Li <i>et al.</i> , 2024)	The Matchboxscope, also known as the ESPressoscope platform, is an open-source, low-cost, and highly portable brightfield microscope designed for capturing micrographs in the field and within cell incubators.	Resolution between 3-4 μm and supports z-stacking for 3D reconstruction. Full schematics, software, and assembly instructions are freely available, encouraging local manufacturing, customisation, and repair. Compact, lightweight, and ideal for remote or rural use, supporting field diagnostics and research without the need for lab infrastructure or continuous internet connectivity.	Typically costs £25 - £65.
Octopi (Li <i>et al.</i> , 2019)	Octopi is a low-cost, open-source, automated slide-scanning microscope designed for clinical diagnostics and pathology. It features motorised scanning, autofocus, and digital imaging, supporting both brightfield and fluorescence modes.	Octopi uses a Raspberry Pi camera or similar CMOS sensor with a high-numerical-aperture lens and 10x or 20x objectives, delivering $\sim 1.3\text{--}2.0\ \mu\text{m}$ resolution, comparable to a basic lab microscope and suitable for clinical screening and AI-based analysis of stained samples. Low power consumption, with some versions running on battery packs or solar systems. Fully open hardware and software, with 3D-printable parts and readily available components, encouraging local assembly, customisation and repair.	£195 - £390 per unit.
OpenFlexure (Collins <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	The OpenFlexure microscope is a low-cost, open-source and 3D-printable digital microscope designed to provide lab-grade performance with high customisability. The microscope supports motorised sample positioning and focus control, enabling	Resolution below 500 nm, with highly customisable components such as objective lenses, cameras and illumination to suit a range of different sample types. Core components can be 3D-printed and designs are open-source. This enables local	£160 for a complete kit of parts needed to assemble the microscope, or £200-£300 for pre-assembled versions.

	automation for scanning large areas and time-lapse imaging.	manufacturing, reducing reliance on expensive imports and lengthy supply chains. Fully functional offline, no internet or cloud dependency.	
--	---	---	--

Enabling access to reagents (or finding ways to not require them)

Our discussion on the key challenges facing LMIC researchers in adopting advanced bioimaging tools revealed that limited access to reagents remains a major bottleneck. Regional procurement strategies need to be explored that can benefit communities of researchers. However, for fundamental research, a lot can still be gained through label-free imaging (Suman *et al.*, 2016) decreasing the reliance on high cost, and long lead times associated with labeled antibodies. By simply enabling robust, quantitative time-lapse imaging, significant experimental results can be obtained, especially with the latest developments in software analysis (Wiggins *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, advances in techniques such as live cell painting and stain prediction may also serve to reduce the need for costly bioimaging reagents (Cross-Zamirski *et al.*, 2022, 2023; Garcia-Fossa *et al.*, 2025).

Enabling access to software advances

To enable widespread uptake by researchers in LMICs, microscopy analysis software needs to strike a balance between analytical capability and computational efficiency. While advanced functionalities, such as deep learning capabilities, multi-dimensional visualisation or single-cell and time-series feature extraction, can offer deeper insights, they often require access to HPC resources that may not be available in resource-limited settings.

Furthermore, to directly address locally relevant research questions posed by LMIC researchers, tools that allow users to retrain models or adjust parameters are essential to enable adaptation to diverse sample types and imaging conditions. Designing software that remains responsive, adaptable, and enables biologically meaningful interpretation of results, whilst being able to run efficiently on modest hardware, is crucial for supporting impactful and accessible research in low-resource environments. See Table 3 for some examples.

Table 3. Examples of advances in accessible image analysis software

Software	Description	Benefit to LMICs
CellPose (Stringer <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	Software built around a neural network with exceptional image segmentation abilities.	The software is highly effective, with some GUI accessibility. The code base could enable expert software engineers in LMICs to repurpose code for their own use cases.
CellProfiler (Carpenter <i>et al.</i> , 2006)	Open-source tools for developing image analysis pipelines with application to high throughput data.	Pipeline-oriented analyses are highly customisable for diverse use cases and allow for computation to be scheduled/managed off-site.
DeepCell Kiosk (Bannon <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	A sophisticated computation management system for faster, more efficient image processing.	LMIC labs can efficiently share computational resources (specifically, but not exclusively, GPU chips) hosted at a small number of hub institutions.
Ilastik (Berg <i>et al.</i> , 2019)	A suite of machine learning algorithms with simple GUIs that enable non-experts to train them.	This project accounts for potential coding skills gaps between software creators and users.
ImageJ/Fiji (Schneider <i>et al.</i> , 2012)	Robust, versatile open-source software with a long history of collaborative development.	The long history and large community of users mean that there is greater chance that users can find advice and assistance with their analyses.
Napari (Sofroniew <i>et al.</i> , 2025)	Image analysis software with particular application to high-dimensional data (e.g. 3 spatial dimensions and/or time).	In combination with appropriate hardware, researchers in LMICs can explore image features that are unavailable in 2d snapshots.
Piximi (Moser <i>et al.</i> , 2024)	A browser/cloud-based platform for image analysis and annotation.	Piximi is user friendly and has functionality for both cloud-based and local computation. This may be particularly useful for compromises that need to be made in terms of local computational resources and data security/sensitivity issues.
ZeroCostDL4Mic (von Chamier <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	A curated library of customisable jupyter notebooks for a variety of bioimaging tasks. By default computation is provided by free Google servers.	These resources are useful both for performing analyses and for training software engineers in LMICs.

Broadening microscopy and imaging analysis technology adoption

Numerous other papers have eloquently discussed potential solutions to increase uptake of microscopy and imaging analysis technologies in resource constrained settings (Reiche *et al.*, 2023; Rahmoon *et al.*, 2024; De Niz *et al.*, 2024; Bajcsy *et al.*, 2025; Aaron *et al.*, 2025; Antunes *et al.*, 2025). With respect to bioimage analysis technology adoption, data pipelines should be implemented, which cover the pathway from hypothesis to publication, integrating quality control, analysis, and reproducibility at each step (Schmied *et al.*, 2024). Minimum standards for participation (e.g., staffing, connectivity, equipment) should be defined to ensure equity and efficacy. New infrastructures are needed to support secure, scalable, and flexible data storage. Although attractive when local hardware is limited, cloud solutions face technical and legal limitations (with respect to data crossing borders) and can be cost-prohibitive, as well as trust challenges related to data ownership and sovereignty. Such challenges with on-site infrastructure (power and networking reliability) can make cloud solutions attractive and hybrid approaches are expected to dominate (Ouyang *et al.*, 2023).

The software landscape is changing quickly. Those working on smaller, less demanding software are in the minority. This skills gap for software is analogous to that for hardware and includes those working to produce modular, customisable (and repairable) hardware and software combinations. There needs to be an emphasis on developing hardware solutions and analytical models that require less computational power than the current state-of-the-art. Finally, personalised and automated guidance systems (e.g., AI tools, tutorials, peer help desks) will help make such advanced analysis accessible. Successful examples include: the image.sc forum (Rueden *et al.*, 2019), GloBIAS help sessions (<https://www.globias.org/activities/globias-free-help>), the Bioimage.IO chatbot (Lei *et al.*, 2024), as well as a growing array of open source educational tools, such as Microtutor (<https://microtutorcourses.org/>), and the Bioimaging Guide (Senft *et al.*, 2023).

In conclusion, we have outlined some key systemic challenges that were discussed in our recent meeting and that hinder the widespread adoption of advanced microscopy and bioimage analysis tools in under-resourced settings. We have also highlighted a superb array of global and community-driven initiatives working to overcome these disparities, with considerable success. However, there is a need for coordinated strategies that go beyond infrastructure and funding. To foster meaningful uptake of these emerging technologies, we need to prioritise knowledge sharing, capacity building, and equitable collaboration. By aligning training, communication, and research priorities with local contexts, the global bioimaging community can create a collaborative ecosystem that drives innovation where it is needed most.

Declarations

The authors declare no competing interests.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Wellcome Trust (310891/Z/24/Z).

References

- Aaron J & Chew T-L (2025). De-risking transformative microscopy technologies for broad adoption. *J Microsc*; DOI: 10.1111/jmi.13400.
- Aaron JS, Jacobs CA, Malacrida L, Keppler A, French P, Fletcher DA, Wood C, Brown CM, Wright GD, Ogawa S, Maina M & Chew T-L (2025). Challenges of microscopy technology dissemination to resource-constrained communities. *Nat Methods*1–5.
- Adair-Rohani H, Zukor K, Bonjour S, Wilburn S, Kuesel AC, Hebert R & Fletcher ER (2013). Limited electricity access in health facilities of sub-Saharan Africa: a systematic review of data on electricity access, sources, and reliability. *Glob Health Sci Pract* 1, 249–261.
- Ahmed A, Daily JP, Lescano AG, Golightly LM & Fasina A (2020). Challenges and strategies for biomedical researchers returning to low- and middle-income countries after training. *Am J Trop Med Hyg* 102, 494–496.

- Antonelli L, Polverino F, Albu A, Hada A, Asteriti IA, Degrassi F, Guarguaglini G, Maddalena L & Guarracino MR (2023). ALFI: Cell cycle phenotype annotations of label-free time-lapse imaging data from cultured human cells. *Sci Data* **10**, 677.
- Antunes MM, Oliveira AG, de Paula CM, Chew T-L, Paula-Neto HA & Menezes GB (2025). Bioimaging Brasil: democratizing in vivo optical microscopy to drive scientific progress across a vast nation. *Nat Methods*; DOI: 10.1038/s41592-025-02686-3.
- Bajcsy P et al. (2025). Enabling global image data sharing in the life sciences. *Nat Methods* **22**, 672–676.
- Bannon D, Moen E, Schwartz M, Borba E, Kudo T, Greenwald N, Vijayakumar V, Chang B, Pao E, Osterman E, Graf W & Van Valen D (2021). DeepCell Kiosk: scaling deep learning-enabled cellular image analysis with Kubernetes. *Nat Methods* **18**, 43–45.
- Berg S, Kutra D, Kroeger T, Straehle CN, Kausler BX, Haubold C, Schiegg M, Ales J, Beier T, Rudy M, Eren K, Cervantes JI, Xu B, Beuttenmueller F, Wolny A, Zhang C, Koethe U, Hamprecht FA & Kreshuk A (2019). Ilastik: Interactive machine learning for (bio)image analysis. *Nat Methods* **16**, 1226–1232.
- Biga R, Nottebaum S, Kozlakidis Z & Psomiadis S (2024). Digitalization of healthcare in LMICs: Digital health and the digital divide based on technological availability and development. In *Sustainable Development Goals Series*, pp. 185–193. Springer International Publishing, Cham.
- Brew-Hammond A (2010). Energy access in Africa: Challenges ahead. *Energy Policy* **38**, 2291–2301.
- Brew-Hammond A & Kemausuor F (2009). Energy for all in Africa — to be or not to be?! *Curr Opin Environ Sustain* **1**, 83–88.
- Brown CM (2018). Careers in core facility management. *Cold Spring Harb Perspect Biol* **10**, a032805.
- Carpenter AE, Jones TR, Lamprecht MR, Clarke C, Kang IH, Friman O, Guertin DA, Chang JH, Lindquist RA, Moffat J, Golland P & Sabatini DM (2006). CellProfiler: image analysis software for identifying and quantifying cell phenotypes. *Genome Biol* **7**, R100.
- von Chamier L et al. (2021). Democratizing deep learning for microscopy with ZeroCostDL4Mic. *Nat Commun* **12**, 2276.
- Chandrasekaran SN et al. (2024). Three million images and morphological profiles of cells treated with matched chemical and genetic perturbations. *Nat Methods*; DOI: 10.1038/s41592-024-02241-6.
- Charani E, Abimbola S, Pai M, Adeyi O, Mendelson M, Laxminarayan R & Rasheed MA (2022). Funders: The missing link in equitable global health research? *PLOS Glob Public Health* **2**, e0000583.
- Chi BH, Belizan JM, Blas MM, Chuang A, Wilson MD, Chibwasha CJ, Farquhar C, Cohen CR & Raj T (2019). Evaluating academic mentorship programs in low- and middle-income country institutions: Proposed framework and metrics. *Am J Trop Med Hyg* **100**, 36–41.
- Chikwari CD, Tadesse AW, Shanaube K, Shepherd A, McQuaid CF & Togun TO (2024). Achieving equitable leadership in Global Health partnerships: barriers experienced and

- strategies to improve grant funding for early- and mid-career researchers. *BMC Glob Public Health* **2**, 17.
- Christiansen EM, Yang SJ, Ando DM, Javaherian A, Skibinski G, Lipnick S, Mount E, O'Neil A, Shah K, Lee AK, Goyal P, Fedus W, Poplin R, Esteva A, Berndl M, Rubin LL, Nelson P & Finkbeiner S (2018). In silico labeling: Predicting fluorescent labels in unlabeled images. *Cell* **173**, 792–803.e19.
- Cimini BA, Tromans-Coia C, Stirling DR, Sivagurunathan S, Senft RA, Ryder PV, Miglietta E, Llanos P, Jamali N, Diaz-Rohrer B, Dasgupta S, Cruz M, Weisbart E & Carpenter AE (2024). A postdoctoral training program in bioimage analysis. *Mol Biol Cell* **35**, e2.
- Collins JT, Knapper J, Stirling J, Mduda J, Mkindi C, Mayagaya V, Mwakajinga GA, Nyakyi PT, Sanga VL, Carbery D, White L, Dale S, Jieh Lim Z, Baumberg JJ, Cicuta P, McDermott S, Vodenicharski B & Bowman R (2020). Robotic microscopy for everyone: the OpenFlexure microscope. *Biomed Opt Express* **11**, 2447–2460.
- Corbat AA, Walther CG, de la Ballina LR, Condon ND, Felder AA, Schätz M, Schmerl B, Sugawara K, Prats C, Klemm A, Levet F, Miura K, Sampaio P, Tischler C, D'Antuono R, Cimini BA & Haase R (2025). GloBIAS: strengthening the foundations of BioImage Analysis. *ArXiv*. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/40671944>.
- Cross-Zamirski JO, Anand P, Williams G, Mouchet E, Wang Y & Schönlieb C-B (2023). Class-guided image-to-image diffusion: Cell painting from Brightfield images with class labels. *arXiv [csCV]*. Available at: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2303.08863>.
- Cross-Zamirski JO, Mouchet E, Williams G, Schönlieb C-B, Turkki R & Wang Y (2022). Label-free prediction of cell painting from brightfield images. *Sci Rep* **12**, 10001.
- Cybulski JS, Clements J & Prakash M (2014). Foldscope: origami-based paper microscope. *PLoS One* **9**, e98781.
- Davé A, Varnai P, Babb R, Raabe B & Amato M (2023). *Landscape review of barriers affecting progress in the field of Bioimaging*. Technopolis Group. Available at: <https://www.technopolis-group.com/report/landscape-review-of-barriers-affecting-progress-in-bioimaging/>.
- De Niz M et al. (2024). Building momentum through networks: Bioimaging across the Americas. *J Microsc* **294**, 420–439.
- Farquharson D, Jaramillo P & Samaras C (2018). Sustainability implications of electricity outages in sub-Saharan Africa. *Nat Sustain* **1**, 589–597.
- Foster V & Steinbuks J (2009). *Paying the price for unreliable power supplies: In-house generation of electricity by firms in Africa*. The World Bank.
- Garcia-Fossa F, Moraes-Lacerda T, Rodrigues-da-Silva M, Diaz-Rohrer B, Singh S, Carpenter AE, Cimini BA & de Jesus MB (2025). Live-cell painting: Image-based profiling in live cells using acridine orange. *Mol Biol Cell* **36**, mr7.
- Ghedira K, Khamessi O, Hkimi C, Kamoun S, Dhamer N, Daassi K, Ben Salah W, Othman H, Belhadj W & Ghorbal Y (2024). Design and implementation of a scalable high-performance computing (HPC) cluster for omics data analysis: achievements, challenges and recommendations in LMICs. *Gigascience* **13**, giae060.
- González-Lorente Á, Hernández-López M, Martín-Álvarez FJ & Mendoza-Jiménez J (2024).

- A comparative analysis of electricity generation in Latin America and the Caribbean using multivariate techniques. *Heliyon* **10**, e39304.
- Gregory J & Sovacool BK (2019). Rethinking the governance of energy poverty in sub-Saharan Africa: Reviewing three academic perspectives on electricity infrastructure investment. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* **111**, 344–354.
- Gujba H, Thorne S, Mulugetta Y, Rai K & Sokona Y (2012). Financing low carbon energy access in Africa. *Energy Policy* **47**, 71–78.
- Guo S-M, Yeh L-H, Folkesson J, Ivanov IE, Krishnan AP, Keefe MG, Hashemi E, Shin D, Chhun BB, Cho NH, Leonetti MD, Han MH, Nowakowski TJ & Mehta SB (2020). Revealing architectural order with quantitative label-free imaging and deep learning. *Elife*; DOI: 10.7554/eLife.55502.
- Haase R, Tischer C, Bankhead P, Miura K & Cimini B (2024). A call for FAIR and open-access training materials to advance BioImage Analysis. ; DOI: 10.31219/osf.io/2zgm. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/2zgm>.
- Hubble JS, Sheeley H & Gallagher A (2020). The role of technical staff in maintaining good health and safety. In *Challenges for Health and Safety in Higher Education and Research Organisations*, pp. 225–251. The Royal Society of Chemistry, Cambridge.
- Isah MB, Muhammad Z, Lawan MM, Alkhamis AI, Goni BW, Oakley SS, Marshall K, Hartig R, Raouf IS-A, Yoshimatsu T, Chagas AM & Maina MB (2024). Setting up a state-of-the-art laboratory in resource limited settings: A case study of the biomedical science research and training centre in Northeast Nigeria. *Eur J Neurosci* **59**, 1681–1695.
- Jacal S, Straubinger FB, Benjamin EO & Buchenrieder G (2022). Economic costs and environmental impacts of fossil fuel dependency in sub-Saharan Africa: A Nigerian dilemma. *Energy Sustain Dev* **70**, 45–53.
- Kilgallon JL, Khanna S, Dey T, Smith TR & Ranganathan K (2023). Open(ing) access: Top health publication availability to researchers in low- and middle-income countries. *Ann Glob Health* **89**, 40.
- Knapper J, Whiteford F, Rosen D, Wadsworth W, Stirling J, Mkindi C, Mduda J, Sanga VL, Nyakyi PT, Mboa Nkoudou TH, Jafsia E, Fadanka S, Hummel K, Anandasabapathy S & Bowman R (2024). Developing the OpenFlexure Microscope towards medical use: technical and social challenges of developing globally accessible hardware for healthcare. *Philos Trans A Math Phys Eng Sci* **382**, 20230257.
- Kpokiri EE, McDonald K, Abraha YG, Osorio L, Nath TC, Talavera-Urdanivia VA, Akinwale OP, Manabe YC, Castelnovo B, Tang W, Yilma D, Mihut M, Ezechi O, Iwelunmor J, Kaba M, Abdissa A & Tucker JD (2024). Health research mentorship in low-income and middle-income countries: a global qualitative evidence synthesis of data from a crowdsourcing open call and scoping review. *BMJ Glob Health* **9**, e011166.
- Launois P, Maher D, Certain E, Ross B & Penkunas MJ (2021). Implementation research training for learners in low- and middle-income countries: evaluating behaviour change after participating in a massive open online course. *Health Res Policy Syst* **19**, 59.
- Lei W, Fuster-Barceló C, Reder G, Muñoz-Barrutia A & Ouyang W (2024). BioImage.IO Chatbot: a community-driven AI assistant for integrative computational bioimaging. *Nat Methods* **21**, 1368–1370.

- Lescano AG, Cohen CR, Raj T, Rispel L, Garcia PJ, Zunt JR, Hamer DH, Heimbürger DC, Chi BH, Ko AI & Bukusi EA (2019). Strengthening mentoring in low- and middle-income countries to advance global health research: An overview. *Am J Trop Med Hyg* **100**, 3–8.
- Li E, Saggiomo V, Ouyang W, Prakash M & Diederich B (2024). ESPressoscope: A small and powerful approach for in situ microscopy. *PLoS One* **19**, e0306654.
- Lightley J, Kumar S, Lim MQ, Garcia E, Görlitz F, Alexandrov Y, Parrado T, Hollick C, Steele E, Roßmann K, Graham J, Broichhagen J, McNeish IA, Roufosse CA, Neil MAA, Dunsby C & French PMW (2023). openFrame: A modular, sustainable, open microscopy platform with single-shot, dual-axis optical autofocus module providing high precision and long range of operation. *J Microsc* **292**, 64–77.
- Li H, Krishnamurthy D, Li E, Vyas P, Akireddy N, Chai C & Prakash M (2020). Squid: Simplifying quantitative imaging platform development and deployment. *bioRxiv*2020.12.28.424613. Available at: <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2020.12.28.424613v1.abstract> [Accessed August 24, 2025].
- Li H, Soto-Montoya H, Voisin M, Valenzuela LF & Prakash M (2019). Octopi: Open configurable high-throughput imaging platform for infectious disease diagnosis in the field. *bioRxiv*684423. Available at: <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/684423v1.abstract> [Accessed September 22, 2025].
- Lin J, Kim D, Tse HT, Tseng P, Peng L, Dhar M, Karumbayaram S & Di Carlo D (2017). High-throughput physical phenotyping of cell differentiation. *Microsyst Nanoeng* **3**, 17013.
- Maina M (2023). Promoting global equality in neuroscience: BioRTC. *Lancet Neurol* **22**, 886.
- Marais EA & Wiedinmyer C (2016). Air quality impact of diffuse and Inefficient Combustion Emissions in Africa (DICE-Africa). *Environ Sci Technol* **50**, 10739–10745.
- Moser LM, Gogoberidze N, Papaleo A, Lucas A, Dao D, Friedrich CA, Paavolainen L, Molnar C, Stirling DR, Hung J, Wang R, Tromans-Coia C, Li B, Evans EL 3rd, Eliceiri KW, Horvath P, Carpenter AE & Cimini BA (2024). Piximi - An Images to Discovery web tool for bioimages and beyond. *bioRxiv*2024.06.03.597232. Available at: <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2024.06.03.597232v2.abstract> [Accessed September 22, 2025].
- Nacis JS et al. (2024). Barriers and enablers to the effective implementation of omics research in low- and middle-income countries. *Nat Biotechnol* **42**, 988–991.
- Ounkomol C, Seshamani S, Maleckar MM, Collman F & Johnson GR (2018). Label-free prediction of three-dimensional fluorescence images from transmitted-light microscopy. *Nat Methods* **15**, 917–920.
- Ouyang W, Eliceiri KW & Cimini BA (2023). Moving beyond the desktop: prospects for practical bioimage analysis via the web. *Front Bioinform* **3**, 1233748.
- Paniagua-Herranz L, Gómez-Villafuertes R, de Agustín-Durán D, Gascón S, Pérez-Sen R, Delicado EG, Miras-Portugal MT & Ortega F (2020). Time-Lapse Video Microscopy and Single Cell Tracking to Study Neural Cell Behavior In Vitro. *Methods Mol Biol* **2150**, 183–194.

- Rahmoon MA, Hobson CM, Aaron JS, Balasubramanian H & Chew T-L (2024). More than just “added value”: The perils of not establishing shared core facilities in resource-constrained communities. *J Microsc* **294**, 440–447.
- Reiche MA, Jacobs CA, Aaron JS, Mizrahi V, Warner DF & Chew T-L (2023). A comprehensive strategy to strengthen bioimaging in Africa through the Africa Microscopy Initiative. *Nat Cell Biol* **25**, 1387–1393.
- Rosen DG, de Mello ES, Dhingra S, Dawsey SM, Knapper J, Bowman R & Anandasabapathy S (2024). Utility of a low-cost 3-D printed microscope for evaluating esophageal biopsies. *Ann 3D Print Med* **13**, 100145.
- Rueden CT, Ackerman J, Arena ET, Eglinger J, Cimini BA, Goodman A, Carpenter AE & Eliceiri KW (2019). Scientific Community Image Forum: A discussion forum for scientific image software. *PLoS Biol* **17**, e3000340.
- Schaefer MA, Nelson HN, Butrum JL, Gronseth JR & Hines JH (2023). A low-cost smartphone fluorescence microscope for research, life science education, and STEM outreach. *Sci Rep* **13**, 2722.
- Schmied C et al. (2024). Community-developed checklists for publishing images and image analyses. *Nat Methods* **21**, 170–181.
- Schneider CA, Rasband WS & Eliceiri KW (2012). NIH Image to ImageJ: 25 years of image analysis. *Nat Methods* **9**, 671–675.
- Senft RA, Diaz-Rohrer B, Colarusso P, Swift L, Jamali N, Jambor H, Pengo T, Brideau C, Llopis PM, Uhlmann V, Kirk J, Gonzales KA, Bankhead P, Evans EL 3rd, Eliceiri KW & Cimini BA (2023). A biologist’s guide to planning and performing quantitative bioimaging experiments. *PLoS Biol* **21**, e3002167.
- Shu F & Larivière V (2024). The oligopoly of open access publishing. *Scientometrics* **129**, 519–536.
- Skandarajah A, Reber CD, Switz NA & Fletcher DA (2014). Quantitative imaging with a mobile phone microscope. *PLoS One* **9**, e96906.
- Smith CL, Kilic O, Schiapparelli P, Guerrero-Cazares H, Kim D-H, Sedora-Roman NI, Gupta S, O’Donnell T, Chaichana KL, Rodriguez FJ, Abbadi S, Park J, Quiñones-Hinojosa A & Levchenko A (2016). Migration Phenotype of Brain-Cancer Cells Predicts Patient Outcomes. *Cell Rep* **15**, 2616–2624.
- Sofroniew N et al. (2025). *napari: a multi-dimensional image viewer for Python*. Zenodo. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3555620> [Accessed May 31, 2023].
- Stringer C, Wang T, Michaelos M & Pachitariu M (2021). Cellpose: a generalist algorithm for cellular segmentation. *Nat Methods* **18**, 100–106.
- Suarez E et al. (2025). Energy-aware operation of HPC systems in Germany. *Front High Perform Comput* **3**, 1520207.
- Suman R, Smith G, Hazel KE, Kasproicz R, Coles M, O’Toole P & Chawla S (2016). Label-free imaging to study phenotypic behavioural traits of cells in complex co-cultures. *Sci Rep* **6**, 22032.
- Szabó S, Moner-Girona M, Kougias I, Bailis R & Bódis K (2016). Identification of advantageous electricity generation options in sub-Saharan Africa integrating existing

resources. *Nat Energy* **1**, 16140.

Velin L, Lartigue J-W, Johnson SA, Zorigtbaatar A, Kanmounye US, Truche P & Joseph MN (2021). Conference equity in global health: a systematic review of factors impacting LMIC representation at global health conferences. *BMJ Glob Health* **6**, e003455.

Walzik MP, Vollmar V, Lachnit T, Dietz H, Haug S, Bachmann H, Fath M, Aschenbrenner D, Abolpour Mofrad S, Friedrich O & Gilbert DF (2015). A portable low-cost long-term live-cell imaging platform for biomedical research and education. *Biosens Bioelectron* **64**, 639–649.

Wiggins L, Lord A, Murphy KL, Lacy SE, O'Toole PJ, Brackenbury WJ & Wilson J (2023). The CellPhe toolkit for cell phenotyping using time-lapse imaging and pattern recognition. *Nat Commun* **14**, 1854.